

Supplementary material collection from "Lifelong exposure to artificial light at night impacts stridulation and locomotion activity patterns in the cricket *Gryllus bimaculatus*":

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Figure S1. Spectrograms of the light bulb used in the anechoic chamber for all experimental groups (LD, LL2, LL5 and LL). (A) 40 lux, (B) 5 lux, (C) 2 lux. The light spectra were recorded using the Sekonic Spectromaster C-700 (North White Plains, NY, USA).

Figure S2. Morphological parameters of male *Gryllus bimaculatus* crickets compared between all four experimental groups LD, LL₂, LL₅ and LL. Mean (\pm S.E.) of body length (n=12, 22, 22, and 41, respectively), wing length (n=12, 22, 22, and 41, respectively), tibia length (n=13, 20, 21, and 41, respectively), femur length (n=13, 20, 21, and 39, respectively), head width (n=12, 22, 22, and 41, respectively), pronotum length (n=12, 22, 22, and 39, respectively) and width (n=12, 22, 22, and 39, respectively), as well as body weight (n=11, 21, 22, and 36, respectively) are presented. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. Inserted: Body condition index of the ratio of the crickets' individual weights divided by their individual lengths and compared between all four experimental groups LD, LL₂, LL₅ and LL (n=11, 22, 21, and 34, respectively), are presented. Single comparisons between treatments did not differ significantly (Kruskal Wallis with Dunn's post-hoc test, $p > 0.09$).

Table S1: Sample sizes of individual male *Gryllus bimaculatus* adult crickets used for each analysis and treatment of the lifelong ALAN experiment. Each column represents another set of analysis on stridulation (left part) or locomotion (right part) behavior. Patterns & percentages include all experimental animals. For the period and acrophase analysis, sample size includes only animals, which period analysis was found significant, hence, all individuals with a synchronized or free-run pattern (but no arrhythmic results). The sample size for the correlation included only individuals, for each both, stridulation and locomotion period results were obtained from the same animal.

	Stridulation		Locomotion		Stridulation and locomotion
Treatment	N total	Rhythmic animals only	N total	Rhythmic animals only	Correlation (only same individuals)
LD	15	15	11	11	10
LL₂	20	19	25	25	19
LL₅	20	19	17	13	10
LL	21	17	40	24	10

Table S2: Percentage of synchronized, free-run and arrhythmic stridulation and locomotion behavior in male *Gryllus bimaculatus* adult crickets exposed to four different lifelong ALAN intensities.

Treatment	Stridulation (%)			Locomotion (%)		
	Synchronized	Free-run	Arrhythmic	Synchronized	Free-run	Arrhythmic
LD	86.67	13.33	0	100	0	0
LL₂	15	80	5	40	60	0
LL₅	15	80	5	29.41	47.06	23.53
LL	0	70.83	29.17	2.38	54.76	42.86

Table S3: Acrophase analyses of stridulation and locomotion activity of individual crickets from the four experimental treatments. Only animals whose activity period was found significant were included in the acrophase analysis. Each datapoint represents the acrophase calculated for five days. The difference data was calculated by subtracting locomotion values from stridulation values of the same individual. Data are presented for all individuals, and separately for those cases where data for both behaviors was available for the same individual.

		Treatment	N	Mean (°)	Vector Length	Median (°)	Variance (°)	Circular SD (°)	SE (°)	95% CI (+/-)
All individuals	Stridulation	LD	15	282.2	0.807	278.4	0.193	37.5	10.6	20.87
		LL ₂	19	258.4	0.404	238.0	0.596	77.2	22.0	43.16
		LL ₅	18	268.8	0.421	274.4	0.579	75.4	21.6	42.37
		LL	17	18.1	0.303	20.0	0.697	88.5	31.7	62.05
	Locomotion	LD	11	87.3	0.673	87.0	0.327	51.0	15.9	31.16
		LL ₂	25	94.9	0.748	100.7	0.252	43.7	8.7	16.97
		LL ₅	13	73.9	0.472	71.9	0.528	70.2	24.0	47.11
		LL	24	4.5	0.255	18.6	0.745	94.8	31.9	62.59
Data for same individuals only	Stridulation	LD	10	278.6	0.93	275.1	0.07	21.8	8.1	15.90
		LL ₂	19	251.8	0.404	231.5	0.596	77.1	22.0	43.11
		LL ₅	9	267.1	0.54	268.3	0.46	63.6	24.7	48.35
		LL	10	355.7	0.41	3.1	0.59	76.5	34.4	67.40
	Locomotion	LD	10	74.0	0.689	84.1	0.311	49.5	16.1	31.59
		LL ₂	19	82.5	0.799	92.1	0.201	38.4	8.7	17.07
		LL ₅	9	77.3	0.462	107.2	0.538	71.2	30.9	60.63
		LL	10	14.6	0.561	17.1	0.439	61.6	22.0	43.09
	Difference	LD	10	209.1	0.644	198.9	0.356	53.7	17.9	35.12
		LL ₂	19	124.9	0.276	127.9	0.724	91.9	33.0	64.70
		LL ₅	9	158.8	0.539	152.4	0.461	63.7	24.7	48.49
		LL	10	84.9	0.148	118.6	0.852	112.0	****	****